

Enhancing Lung Cancer Treatment Outcome Prediction through Semantic Feature Engineering Using Large Language Models

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ABSTRACT

Accurate prediction of treatment outcome in lung cancer is critical but challenged by the sparsity and heterogeneity of real-world data, as traditional models fail to leverage deep semantic context. To overcome this, we propose and validate a novel framework using Large Language Models (LLMs) as "Goal-oriented Knowledge Curators" to generate high-fidelity, task-specific features. We predicted 1-year survival by systematically comparing three feature representation strategies using Lab, Genomic, and Medication data. We benchmarked our proposed LLM-summarizer against an expert-engineered numerical baseline and a direct text-embedding model, and an end-to-end transformer model. Our "Goal-oriented Knowledge Curators" approach achieved a superior mean AUC-ROC of 0.803 (95% CI: 0.799-0.807) and significantly outperformed all baselines. An ablation study further confirmed the synergistic value of combining all three modalities. We demonstrate a hierarchy in data representation, where LLM-driven summarization outperforms traditional and simple embedding methods. Our findings suggest that LLMs as "goal-oriented knowledge curators" provide a powerful solution to the challenges of sparse clinical data, proving that the quality of semantic representation is paramount for accurate prediction.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Applied computing • Artificial intelligence • Natural language processing • Medical Informatics

KEYWORDS

Treatment Outcome Prediction, Multi-Modal Data, Large Language Models (LLMs), Semantic Representation, Lung Cancer

1 Introduction

Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, accounting for over 1.8 million deaths annually [1]. Despite advances in diagnosis and therapy, the treatment outcome for lung cancer patients is often poor, with five-year survival rates languishing below 20% in most populations [1, 2]. Accurate prediction of treatment outcome is essential for informed clinical decision-making, guiding treatment selection, risk stratification, and the allocation of scarce medical resources [3, 4].

For decades, the TNM staging system has served as the foundation for lung cancer treatment outcome, providing critical guidance based on the anatomical extent of disease [5, 6]. While it remains the gold standard for initial risk stratification, substantial clinical evidence reveals that patients within the same TNM stage can exhibit markedly different outcomes [7, 8]. This variability arises from complex biological heterogeneity, which includes molecular driver mutations, the tumor immune microenvironment, and key laboratory-based biomarkers [9]. As a result, there is a growing imperative to develop more accurate, personalized models by integrating multi-modal data sources—including laboratory results, genomic profiles, and medication histories—to capture the multifaceted determinants of patient outcomes.

Numerous studies have explored using traditional machine learning to integrate multi-modal structured data, such as concatenating feature vectors from different sources [10-13]. However, these models treat each feature as an isolated, context-free data point. While they can identify correlations, they fail to capture the underlying biological or clinical meaning that expert clinicians extract by synthesizing information holistically across modalities [14]. This gap highlights a critical need for computational paradigms capable of performing deeper semantic reasoning on complex biomedical data.

Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) show promise for biomedical applications [15, 16]. Fine-tuned multimodal systems (e.g., Med-PaLM Multimodal) can integrate diverse inputs [17], and advanced prompt engineering techniques (e.g.,

Figure 1: Overview of the Three Feature Engineering Strategies. The figure illustrates the three systematic approaches compared in this study. (A) The Expert-Engineered Baseline transforms multi-modal clinical data into a structured numerical feature vector based on pre-defined domain knowledge. (B) The Contextual Text Embedding enriches the raw data with detailed descriptions from biomedical databases to create modality-specific text profiles, which are then embedded. (C) Our Proposed 'Goal-oriented Knowledge Curators' Framework utilizes LLMs to generate a high-fidelity, semantic summary for each modality, and the embeddings of these summaries are used as the final predictive features.

Medprompt [18]) can approach specialist performance without task-specific training. However, practical barriers remain. Fine-tuning demands large, high-quality labeled datasets, while sophisticated few-shot prompting depends on many well-crafted exemplars. In clinical prediction, such resources are rare and datasets are typically small, sparse, and heterogeneous. This creates a clear disconnect: the most powerful LLM strategies are often unusable in real-world clinical settings, withholding advanced AI capabilities precisely where they are most urgently needed.

In this study, we address this gap with a framework that uses LLMs for modality-specific semantic summarization. Rather than asking a model to make an end-to-end prediction from all data at once, we first produce goal-aligned summaries per modality (laboratory, genomics, medication). Each summary distills the salient, task-relevant information available in that modality and preserves an interpretable intermediate that can be audited in clinical workflows. The summaries are then embedded and supplied to a lightweight classifier.

Our inputs are assay-grounded, clinician-facing profiles. The genomics modality is a clinically deployed, expert-curated targeted panel of 271 cancer-related genes, reviewed by oncology and molecular genetics teams and focused on actionable driver and resistance biology. In routine care this panel-level genomics is available to a minority of patients due to cost and access constraints, making it pharmacogenomic high-value when present. Serial laboratory tests capture current physiological state (e.g., inflammation and nutritional status). Structured medication history

reflects therapeutic intent and disease trajectory. Modeling these three streams together aligns with how oncology teams actually review patient data.

We evaluate three representation strategies for the same cohort and task (1-year survival): (i) an expert-engineered numerical baseline, (ii) a contextual text-embedding baseline that embeds detailed modality profiles from biomedical knowledge bases, and (iii) the proposed modality-specific summarization approach that first produces goal-aligned modality summaries and then embeds them. All models are assessed with repeated stratified cross-validation under identical protocols.

Our results show a clear hierarchy of representations. Modality-specific summarization achieves the best performance (AUC-ROC 0.803; AUC-PRC 0.859), exceeding both the expert-engineered numerical baseline (AUC-ROC 0.619; AUC-PRC 0.713) and the contextual embedding baseline (AUC-ROC 0.678; AUC-PRC 0.771). An ablation study confirms synergy across modalities, and SHAP analyses indicate balanced contributions from laboratory, genomics, and medication features. Additionally, a long-context BERT baseline with a classification head performed comparably to the contextual embedding baseline, further underscoring that task-aligned summarization, rather than generic self-attention over long profiles, drives the observed gains.

In summary, the key contributions of this work are:

1. We introduce a modality-specific LLM summarization framework that converts assay-grounded clinical inputs into compact, interpretable features suitable for audit and deployment in real-world oncology.
2. We provide a rigorous, stepwise comparison demonstrating a representation hierarchy from numerical encoding to contextual embedding to goal-aligned summarization.
3. We show that preserving pharmacogenomically rich but scarce panel-level genomics alongside laboratory and medication streams improves prediction and maintains interpretability.
4. We offer empirical evidence—including ablations and model comparisons—that explicit summarization, not generic self-attention, drives the observed gains in this setting.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 details data sources and the semantic feature engineering pipeline. Section 3 describes the modeling strategies and evaluation protocol. Section 4 presents experimental results and ablation analyses. Section 5 discusses implications, limitations, and future research directions.

2 Methods

This section details the systematic methodology employed to develop and evaluate our treatment outcome prediction models. We describe the study cohort, data sources, the three distinct feature engineering strategies, and the rigorous statistical validation framework used to compare their performance.

2.1 Study Design and Patient Cohort

This study was designed as a retrospective cohort analysis using de-identified data from the electronic health record (EHR) system, conducted under Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval. For anonymization during review, the IRB protocol identifier is withheld; all analyses were performed on de-identified data within a secure computing environment. We identified all adult patients diagnosed with lung cancer between 2011-06-29 and 2022-10-18. To ensure a clear treatment window and mitigate lead-time bias, we implemented a 90-day landmark design. Only patients who survived at least 90 days following their initial diagnosis were included in the final analysis. The primary endpoint was 1-year all-cause mortality, calculated from this 90-day landmark point.

We initially identified all adult patients diagnosed with lung cancer between 2011-06-29 and 2022-10-18 who had undergone targeted genomic panel testing, resulting in a potential cohort of 662 patients. From this group, patients were excluded if they lacked sufficient data across all three required modalities (Lab, Genomics, and Medication) within the specified timeframes. “Sufficient data” was operationalized as the availability of all three modalities within the 90-day window from diagnosis to the landmark time. All inclusion/exclusion decisions were applied prior to feature construction and strictly within training folds to prevent

information leakage (see section 2.7). This filtering step yielded 184 patients with complete multi-modal data.

2.2 Cohort Characteristics

After applying all inclusion and exclusion criteria, our final study cohort consisted of 184 patients. The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of this cohort are summarized in Table 1. The population had a mean age of 65.1 years and a balanced sex distribution. Critically, the cohort represents a high-risk population, with 71.7% of patients having metastatic disease already documented at the 90-day landmark. Furthermore, 45.7% of patients presented with at least one major comorbidity. The median number of mutated genes and prescribed drug classes per patient were 5 and 9, respectively, reflecting the clinical and molecular complexity of this real-world dataset. Ultimately, 36.4% of the patients in the cohort died within one year from the landmark point.

Table 1. Demographics and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Cohort (N=184)

Characteristic	Value at Landmark
Demographics	
Age, years (Mean ± SD)	65.1 ± 10.4
Sex, n (%)	
Male	90 (48.9)
Female	94 (51.1)
Clinical Characteristics	
Metastatic Disease, n (%)	132 (71.7)
Key Comorbidities*, n (%)	84 (45.7)
Key Modality Summaries	
Laboratory Values	
Albumin (g/dL), Mean ± SD	3.8 ± 0.6
Hemoglobin (g/dL), Mean ± SD	11.7 ± 2.3
Platelets (K/uL), Mean ± SD	241.7 ± 119.0
Genomic and Medication Profile	
Mutated Genes per Patient, Median [IQR]	5 [3-7]
Drug Classes per Patient, Median [IQR]	9 [7-11]
Outcome	
Died within 1-Year from Landmark, n (%)	67 (36.4)

*Key comorbidities include COPD, Coronary Artery Disease, Congestive Heart Failure, Chronic Kidney Disease, Diabetes, Cerebrovascular Disease, or Connective Tissue Disease diagnosed at or before the 90-day landmark. These clinical variables were used to characterize the cohort. SD: Standard Deviation; IQR: Interquartile Range. All data presented as n (%), unless otherwise specified.

<p>(A) Genomic Profile Example:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mutation Gene: TP53 - Function: This gene encodes a tumor suppressor protein containing transcriptional activation, DNA binding, and oligomerization domains. The encoded protein responds to diverse cellular stresses ... - KEGG Pathways: MAPK signaling pathway; Cell cycle; p53 signaling pathway; PI3K-Akt signaling pathway; Apoptosis; ... - Biological Processes: negative regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II; - Molecular Functions: transcription cis-regulatory region binding; transcription cis-regulatory region binding; 2. Mutation Gene: KRAS - Function : This gene, a Kirsten ras oncogene homolog from the mammalian ras gene family, encodes ... 3. Mutation Gene: ... 4. Mutation Gene: ... 	<p>(B) LLM Summarizer Output Example:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Summary: The patient's genomic profile, characterized by concurrent TP53 and KRAS mutations, suggests an aggressive tumor biology and a guarded progress. The activating KRAS mutation will ... 2. Key domains <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Activated Oncogenic driver pathways: Ras, MAPK, PI3K-Akt , ... 2.2 Inactivated Tumor suppressor pathways: p53, Cell cycle control, Apoptosis ... 2.3 Therapeutic implications: Likely resistance to chemotherapy relying on p53 function. ... 3. Key positive factors: None, 4. Key negative factors: (1) Concurrent mutation of a potent oncogene (KRAS) and a critical tumor suppressor (TP53). (2) Activation of multiple pro-growth signaling pathways. ...
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Figure 2: Comparison of Feature Representation for a Hypothetical Patient's Genomic Profile. This figure illustrates the distinct inputs for CTE Model and GKC Model using a hypothetical patient profile. (A) The input for CTE Model is a long-form textual profile, created by concatenating detailed descriptions for each dysregulated hallmark domain from public knowledge bases. (B) In contrast, the input for GKC Model is a concise, goal-oriented summary generated by the 'Goal-oriented Knowledge Curators' LLM. This summary synthesizes the raw information from (A) into a high-fidelity narrative focused specifically on implications of treatment outcomes, such as the synergistic effect of the co-mutations and likely immunotherapy resistance. This process transforms noisy, descriptive text into a dense, feature-rich summary for the downstream classifier.

2.3 Data Sources and Preprocessing

We extracted and integrated three distinct data modalities for each patient within the 90-day window from diagnosis to the landmark time.

- Medication Data (Med): We extracted prescription records for 64 drugs from the EHR. This list was compiled by identifying 38 anti-cancer agents prescribed to our cohort from a list of FDA-approved lung cancer drugs, and adding 26 key supportive care drugs also administered to these patients. This selection was based on a review of the most frequently prescribed medications for this specific patient cohort, reflecting actual clinical practice. To build contextual profiles, we programmatically parsed the full DrugBank database [19] to extract detailed information for each drug, including its description, mechanism-of-action, indication, pharmacodynamics, and toxicity. Individual drugs were then grouped into 27 clinically meaningful classes (e.g., Platinum-Based Chemotherapy, PD-1/PD-L1 Checkpoint Inhibitors, Strong Opioids) based on their mechanism of action.

- Genomic Data (Gene): We utilized data from a targeted sequencing panel of 271 cancer-related genes. This panel is clinically deployed and expert-curated at our institution, covering actionable driver and resistance biology. All gene names were first normalized to their official HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee (HGNC) symbols. To create rich semantic profiles, we programmatically retrieved annotation data from established biomedical knowledge bases. This included functional summaries from the NCBI Gene database [20], pathway information from the KEGG database [21], and functional annotations (Biological Processes, Molecular Functions) from the Gene Ontology (GO) database [22, 23].

- Laboratory Data (Lab): Based on a literature review in lung cancer, we selected 10 laboratory tests that are well-established [24, 25] as

markers for systemic inflammation, nutritional status, and overall physiological resilience. These tests include Albumin, Platelets, and components of the complete blood count with differential (e.g., Neutrophils, Lymphocytes). For each patient, we collected the five most recent values for these tests within the 90-day landmark period. If fewer than five values were available, the series was padded using the most recent available observation (last-observation-carried-forward). Laboratory units were harmonized to institutional reference ranges prior to normalization; missingness, out-of-range entries, and biologically implausible values were screened and resolved by predefined rules.

2.4 Feature Engineering Strategies

We systematically compared three distinct strategies for representing the multi-modal data, each building upon the last. The fundamental difference between our key models is conceptually illustrated using a hypothetical patient's genomic profile in Figure 2.

- ENF (Expert-Engineered Numerical Features) Model: This baseline represents the traditional tabular data-based approach (Figure. 1A). Features consisted of a single numerical vector per patient, the five most recent lab values of 10 lab tests, the count of mutated genes, and a binary indicator (0/1) for the prescription of each of the 27 medication classes. Missing medication and genomic entries were treated as absent and encoded as zeros. We normalized the lab values for each lab test to preserve each lab test data's information range because each lab test has a different Unit of test and normal criteria. To mitigate the risk of overfitting in our data-scarce setting, we applied Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to this concatenated vector to create a final, lower-dimensional, dense feature set. All transformations (scaling, PCA) were fit within training folds only to avoid leakage.

- CTE (Contextual Text Embedding) Model: This model was designed to test the value of adding semantic context directly from biomedical databases (Figure. 1B). For each patient, we generated three modality-specific text profiles by concatenating detailed, pre-written descriptions for each relevant data point, as exemplified in Figure 2A. These profiles were enriched with information from biomedical databases (DrugBank, Gene Ontology, KEGG) and included functional summaries for genes, mechanisms of action for medications, and the values and normal ranges for lab tests. The complete text profile for each modality was then encoded and concatenated into a final feature vector.

- E2E (End-to-End Transformer) Model: As a direct response to reviewer feedback, we added a powerful end-to-end baseline. This model uses a state-of-the-art long-context transformer (ModernBERT) fine-tuned directly on the same long-form contextual text profiles used by the CTE model. This approach tests the hypothesis that a large transformer model can automatically learn to summarize and predict without an explicit knowledge curation step.

- GKC (Goal-oriented Knowledge Curators) Model: This is our proposed framework (Figure 1C). It generates a separate, goal-oriented modality summary for each modality, an example of which is shown in Figure 2B. The detailed methodology for this LLM-based summarization, a core contribution of this work, is described in Section 2.5. The resulting three text summaries were then independently embedded, and their vectors concatenated, creating a multi-channel semantic feature vector that preserves modality-specific insights for the downstream classifier. The only architectural difference between CTE and GKC is the LLM summarization step; the embedding model, dimensionality selection, classifier family, hyperparameter search space, and cross-validation protocol are identical.

2.5 LLM-based Semantic Summarization Pipeline

In our work, 'Semantic Summarization' is defined as a goal-oriented process that involves (1) extracting insights relevant to the prediction target, (2) synthesizing relationships between disparate data points, and (3) generating an interpretive narrative, going beyond simple compression. The core of our proposed model (GKC Model) is a pipeline designed to transform the verbose, context-rich text profiles used by CTE Model into high-fidelity, treatment outcomes related features. As illustrated in Figure 2, this process uses an LLM to synthesize the raw, descriptive information (Fig. 2A) into a concise, goal-oriented narrative focused specifically on implications for treatment outcomes (Fig. 2B).

This was achieved by prompting the LLM to act as a clinical expert and generate a structured JSON report for each modality. This strategy, a major contribution of this work, was designed to guide the LLM to act as a domain expert for each modality and incorporates three key principles:

1. Structured Output: To ensure consistency and enable automated parsing, the LLM was instructed to generate its analysis in a structured JSON format with pre-defined keys. We constrained outputs to a schema with required fields: summary, key_domains, therapy_implications, positives, and negatives.

2. Persona-based Role-playing: The prompt assigned the LLM a specific expert role (e.g., 'clinical pharmacologist' or 'systems biologist') tailored to each modality, aligning its reasoning with domain-specific knowledge. This role prompting is used only to steer framing; we do not invoke external tools or knowledge bases at generation time.

3. Specialized Task Guidance: A core innovation was specializing the prompts for each data type. For instance, the Gene prompt focused on oncogenic pathway dysregulation, while the Medication prompt assessed treatment intent and disease burden, and the Lab report evaluated inflammation and nutritional status.

This approach forced the LLM to synthesize modality-specific insights through a clinically relevant lens, rather than simply restating information. Generation was strictly "from-context": the model summarized only the provided modality profiles. Decoding was deterministic (temperature=0.0; top_k=1) to ensure reproducibility and reduce hallucination variance.

2.6 LLMs Model and Embedding Specifications

- LLM for Knowledge Curation: All modality summaries for GKC Model were generated using Gemini 2.0 Flash [26], chosen for its strong performance for Medical expert-annotated hallucination test including chronological ordering, lab data understating and diagnosis prediction [27]. To ensure reproducibility and minimize variability, all prompts were executed with deterministic settings (temperature=0.0, top_k=1). A zero-shot prompting strategy was employed. No retrieval or external knowledge calls were used; summaries are produced solely from the constructed modality profiles. The complete prompts are provided in the Supplementary Document

- Text Embedding and Dimensionality Reduction: All textual data for both CTE Model and GKC Model were converted into dense feature vectors using Google's text-embedding-005 model (Gecko) [28]. The task_type parameter was set to CLASSIFICATION to optimize the embeddings for this downstream task. The model initially generates a high-dimensional vector of 768, which poses a significant risk of overfitting for our cohort size (N=184). To address this, we treated the final embedding dimension as a key hyperparameter. Following the model's API specifications, we employed a truncation of the 768-dimensional vector to a lower dimension. The optimal output dimension was determined empirically as part of the hyperparameter tuning phase of the classifier, ensuring a balance between information richness and model generalizability. To empirically validate this choice, we compared Gecko against a recent biomedical-specific embedding model; Gecko demonstrated significantly higher performance on our downstream task (see Appendix D for full experimental details and results).

2.7 Predictive Modeling and Evaluation

- Classifier: To ensure that our findings were robust and not dependent on a single algorithm, we benchmarked a suite of standard machine learning classifiers. This included tree-based ensembles (XGBoost, Random Forest), a neural network (Fully Connected Neural Networks), a kernel method (Support Vector Machine), and a linear model (Logistic Regression with ElasticNet). The final classifier for reporting all primary results was selected based on the highest and most stable performance in this benchmark, with detailed comparative results presented in Section 4.4.

- E2E Model: We trained a long-context transformer (ModernBERT [29], 8,192-token context) with a classification head under the same splits and evaluation protocol. We fine-tuned ModernBERT-base (~149M parameters) with a classification head using a learning rate of $3e-5$, 8 epochs, a linear scheduler with a 10% warm-up ratio, max sequence length 8,192 (ensuring no truncation of our longest profiles), and early stopping on validation AUC-ROC within inner folds. Training used the same repeated stratified CV splits as above.

- Validation and Hyperparameter Tuning: We employed a 10-times repeated 5-fold stratified cross-validation strategy to ensure robust performance evaluation. Within each training fold, an inner cross-validation loop was used for hyperparameter tuning via a grid search.

- Evaluation Metrics: Model performance was primarily assessed using the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC). We also report the Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PRC), which are informative metrics for datasets with potential class imbalance.

2.8 Statistical and Interpretation Analysis

- Statistical Significance: To compare the performance distributions of different models obtained from the 10 repeated CV runs, we used the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test, as it makes no assumptions about the underlying data distribution. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

- Confidence Intervals: 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for the mean performance metrics were calculated using bootstrapping with 1000 resamples.

- Feature Contribution: For our best-performing model (DES Model), we used SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations [30]) to quantify the relative importance and contribution of the features derived from each of the three data modalities (Lab, Gene, Medication).

3 Results

This section systematically evaluates the predictive performance of our proposed models on the task of predicting 1-year survival. We first present the primary comparison between our proposed 'Goal-oriented Knowledge Curator' model (GKC Model) and three

baseline models (ENF Model, CTE Model, and E2E Model) to validate our core hypothesis. Subsequently, we demonstrate the robustness of our classifier choice through a comparative analysis with various machine learning algorithms. Finally, we provide a detailed ablation study and a modality contribution analysis with SHAP to dissect the synergistic effects of multi-modality and the importance of each data type.

3.1 Experimental Design and Evaluation Metrics

All models were evaluated on 1-year survival prediction in a cohort of 184 lung cancer patients, using a 10-times repeated 5-fold cross-validation scheme for robust performance assessment. We report several key performance metrics, including Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC) and Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PRC). The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to determine statistical significance between models, ensuring all comparisons followed identical validation procedures.

3.2 Primary Finding: Superiority of LLM-based Semantic Summarization

Figure 3: Comparative Performance of Feature Engineering Strategies. Comparison of mean AUC-ROC and AUC-PRC across three feature engineering strategies. Our proposed 'Goal-oriented Knowledge Curator' approach (GKC Model) significantly outperforms the traditional numerical baseline (ENF Model), the direct contextual text embedding model (CTE Model) and an end-to-end transformer baseline (E2E Model). Error bars represent standard deviation (SD). Symbol * above box plots between models represents that a p-value is less than 0.05 for both metrics.

Our primary analysis, visually summarized in Figure 3, reveals a clear and consistent performance hierarchy across the three feature engineering strategies. The expert-engineered numerical feature baseline (ENF Model) achieved a modest performance with a mean AUC-ROC of 0.62 (95% CI: 0.618-0.621) and a mean AUC-PRC of 0.71 (95% CI: 0.708-0.718). The first step of semantic enrichment—applying direct embedding to contextual text from biomedical databases (CTE Model)—yielded some level of improvement, with the AUC-ROC and AUC-PRC increasing to 0.68 (95% CI: 0.675-0.681) and 0.77 (95% CI: 0.768-0.775), respectively. This initial gain underscores the inherent value of providing semantic context that is lost in purely numerical representations.

To test an end-to-end model (E2E Model), we fine-tuned a state-of-the-art long-context transformer, ModernBERT, on the same inputs of CTE Model. This model achieved a mean AUC-ROC of 0.675 (95% CI: 0.663–0.685) and an AUC-PRC of 0.781 (95% CI: 0.772–0.791). A Wilcoxon signed-rank test confirmed that there was no statistically significant difference in performance between the E2E Model and CTE models ($p=0.770$ for AUC-ROC, $p=0.105$ for AUC-PRC).

Critically, the final and most substantial performance leap was achieved by our proposed GKC Model, the GKC Model. This model, which utilizes LLM-generated summaries for each modality, reached a mean AUC-ROC of 0.803 (95% CI: 0.799-0.807) and a mean AUC-PRC of 0.859 (95% CI: 0.855-0.862). This represents a statistically significant improvement over both the traditional baseline (ENF Model, $p < 0.05$ for both metrics) and the contextual text embedding baseline (CTE Model, $p < 0.05$ for both metrics), and the end-to-end transformer model (E2E Model, $p < 0.05$ for both metrics). Furthermore, to contextualize our framework's use of a general-purpose LLM, we evaluated a strong alternative using a large, biomedical-specific LLM (MedFound-176B [31]) for both the summarization and subsequent embedding tasks. This specialized pipeline yielded a mean AUC-ROC of 0.752 and AUC-PRC of 0.832, a performance significantly lower than our GKC model. (The detailed methodology for this experiment is provided in Appendix C).

3.3 Robustness of the Predictive Classifier

To identify the optimal classifier for our novel LLM-generated features, we benchmarked the performance of a suite of standard machine learning algorithms using the identical feature set from GKC Model. As illustrated in Figure 4, our analysis revealed that tree-based ensemble methods provided superior performance. XGBoost achieved the highest AUROC of 0.80 (± 0.006), followed closely by Random Forest at 0.76 (± 0.007). In contrast, models such as the Fully Connected Neural Network (FCNN) yielded lower and more variable performance (AUC-ROC 0.72 ± 0.012). This outcome highlights the unsuitability of high-capacity models like neural networks for data-scarce clinical settings ($N=184$), where they are prone to overfitting. On the other hand, the superior performance of tree-based ensembles like XGBoost, suggests their

Figure 4: Comparative Performance of Predictive Classifiers on GKC Model Features. Mean AUC-ROC and AUC-PRC for five standard machine learning algorithms trained on the LLM-generated features from GKC Model. XGBoost achieved the highest performance across both metrics, justifying its selection as the primary classifier for this study.

inherent regularization and ability to model complex interactions are particularly effective in this data-scarce regime, even with dense embedding features. Based on these results, we selected XGBoost as the primary classifier for all comparisons in this study.

3.4 Analysis of Modality Contribution and Synergy

3.4.1 Synergistic Effect of Multi-Modality (Ablation Study).

To dissect the sources of GKC Model's predictive power, we conducted an ablation study by training the model on all seven possible combinations of the three modalities. The results, illustrated in Figure 5, reveal two key insights. First, among single modalities, Medication data provided the strongest standalone treatment outcome signal (AUC-ROC: 0.64), outperforming both Gene (AUC-ROC: 0.59) and Lab (AUC-ROC: 0.58) data.

Second, and more importantly, the study demonstrates a powerful synergistic effect when modalities are combined. The performance consistently increased with the addition of more data types. A notable synergy was observed between Genomic and Medication data, with the Gene+Med combination achieving a strong AUC-ROC of 0.76 and AUC-PRC of 0.83. However, the highest performance was achieved only when all three modalities were integrated (Lab+Gene+Med), reaching a final AUC-ROC of 0.80

and AUC-PRC of 0.86. This result confirms that each modality provides unique and complementary information, and that their holistic integration is essential for maximal predictive accuracy.

Figure 5: Ablation Study of Modality Contribution to Treatment Outcome Prediction Performance. Mean AUC-ROC and AUC-PRC performance from an ablation study on GKC Model, evaluating all combinations of Lab, Gene, and Med data. The results show a clear stepwise improvement as modalities are combined, with the full three-modality model achieving the highest performance. This demonstrates that each modality provides complementary, non-redundant information.

3.4.2 Modality Importance in the Final Model (SHAP Analysis). To provide a mechanistic explanation for our model's success, we analyzed the contribution of each modality within the final three-modality model using SHAP. The results are visualized in Figure 6. The analysis revealed a remarkably balanced contribution from the three feature streams. The mean global SHAP contributions across the entire cohort were nearly identical (Medication: 33.2%, Gene: 33.9%, Lab: 32.9%), as shown in the pie chart (Fig. 6A).

Furthermore, the box plot illustrating the distribution of SHAP contributions for each individual patient (Fig. 6B) reinforces this finding of equitable importance. Pairwise statistical tests confirmed that these minor visual variations were not significant ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons). This balanced contribution provides strong evidence for the success of our modality-specific approach: rather than relying on a single dominant data type, the classifier learns to flexibly weigh and combine all three independent, high-fidelity information streams provided by the LLM agents.

Figure 6: Balanced Contribution of Multi-Modal Features to Treatment Outcome Prediction. SHAP analysis of the final prediction model. (A) The mean global feature importance is almost equally distributed among the Lab, Gene, and Medication modalities. (B) Box plots showing the distribution of per-patient contributions confirm this balanced interplay. This result provides a mechanistic explanation for our model's success, demonstrating that it learns by flexibly integrating all three independent information streams rather than relying on a single dominant modality.

3.5 In-depth Qualitative Case Study

To provide a direct, mechanistic assessment of our Goal-oriented Knowledge Curator (GKC) framework, we present a qualitative analysis of a representative patient case. This patient presented with a complex genomic profile, including seven key mutations (REL, RICTOR, MDM2, CDK4, ALK, ATR, and KRAS). The raw input for the LLM is a long-form text profile generated by concatenating detailed descriptions for each gene from biomedical databases (NCBI, KEGG, GO). This process results in a lengthy, semi-structured document that exemplifies the "data-scarce, context-overloaded" challenge, characterized by information overload, redundancy of key pathways, and a lack of focus on the specific task of cancer prognosis.

The LLM-based GKC transforms this noisy input into a concise, structured JSON report designed to be directly useful for prognostic prediction. A direct comparison of the input and output reveals three key value-adding cognitive tasks performed by the LLM. First, the GKC acts as an effective noise filter. It successfully identifies and discards irrelevant information (e.g., the non-cancer associations for REL) and de-duplicates redundant pathway mentions, distilling the verbose academic descriptions into a focused summary. Second, and most critically, the GKC goes beyond summarization to perform clinical inference. It synthesizes information across multiple genes, a task impossible without a degree of biomedical knowledge.

- Identifying Synergistic Effects: The raw input lists KRAS and MDM2 as separate entities. The LLM, however, infers their dangerous synergy, explicitly stating in its summary: "The presence of mutant KRAS alongside MDM2 amplification

indicates strong activation of proliferative and survival signaling pathways." It further highlights this as a key negative prognostic factor, noting the "Concurrent KRAS mutation and MDM2 amplification." This inference of a "double-hit" on critical pathways is a high-level insight does not present in the source text.

- **Inferring Higher-Level Concepts:** The LLM synthesizes the effects of all seven mutations to form a holistic clinical picture. It correctly interprets the combined impact as an "aggressive tumor phenotype," a "highly proliferative, therapy-resistant tumor," and a state of "genomic instability"—all expert-level concepts that are conclusions derived from the data, not statements present in the data itself.

Finally, the GKC fundamentally restructures the data in a goal-oriented manner. It converts a gene-centric list into a prognostically-focused report with fields like "prognostic summary" and "key negative factors", a form of feature engineering.

This case study provides direct evidence that our GKC framework is not merely compressing text; it is performing goal-oriented knowledge curation. It actively distills, synthesizes, and restructures information to create a high-signal, feature-rich representation that is vastly superior to the raw input for the specific task of predicting treatment outcomes. This analysis provides a clear, mechanistic explanation for the significant performance lift observed in our quantitative results. The full, verbatim input profile and the resulting JSON summary for this patient are provided in Appendix A for detailed comparison.

3.6 Summary of Main Findings

In summary, our results establish a clear hierarchy of feature representation, where our proposed 'Goal-oriented Knowledge Curator' framework (GKC Model) robustly outperformed all baselines. Furthermore, ablation and contribution analyses confirmed that this superior performance arises from the synergistic integration of complementary signals from Lab, Genomic, and Medication data modalities. These findings collectively validate the effectiveness of using LLMs as goal-oriented knowledge curators for small, complex clinical datasets.

4 Discussion

In this study, we addressed the challenge of prediction of treatment outcomes in lung cancer using sparse, real-world multi-modal data. Our findings show that leveraging LLMs as 'Goal-oriented Knowledge Curators' to generate high-quality semantic features substantially and significantly outperforms both conventional feature engineering (ENF Model) and text-embedding approaches (CTE Model), as well as a powerful end-to-end transformer baseline (E2E Model). Here, we interpret the significance of these findings, contextualize them within the broader literature, discuss underlying mechanisms, and outline implications for future research in clinical AI.

Our approach shows that the "small data" problem is not solely about sample size, but about the loss of latent clinical meaning in

conventional features. By transforming raw data into narrative, interpretable summaries, we enable machine learning models to access the deeper clinical context typically leveraged by human experts.

Our ablation studies confirm the necessity of a holistic, multi-modal approach. The highest predictive performance was achieved only by integrating all three modalities (Lab, Gene, Med; AUC-ROC 0.803 and AUC-PRC 0.859), far surpassing any single or pairwise combination. This demonstrates that each modality contributes unique, complementary information, which we interpret through the lens of different temporal and biological perspectives:

- Medication Data ("The Therapeutic Trajectory"): The strongest single predictor, reflecting both treatment intent and overall patient status.
- Genomic Data ("The Blueprint"): Static biological features that enable precision oncology when combined with therapy data (e.g., high Gene+Med synergy, AUC-ROC 0.76 and AUC-PRC 0.83).
- Lab Data ("The Dynamic State"): High-resolution snapshots of current patient physiology, synthesized by the LLM into concepts like "inflammation" or "nutritional status."

Our new experiment comparing the GKC framework to a pipeline using a large, biomedical-specific LLM (MedFound-176B) provides a noteworthy insight. The finding that our approach with a general-purpose LLM significantly outperformed the specialized one is counter-intuitive. We hypothesize this is due to the nature of our "goal-oriented knowledge curator" task. The objective is not simply to extract biomedical facts, but to synthesize complex inputs into a prognostically-focused summary according to a specific set of instructions. A powerful general-purpose model, trained on a vast and diverse range of text styles, may be superior at this specific task of complex instruction-following and logical synthesis than a model whose knowledge, while deeper, may be more narrowly focused on recalling facts from academic texts.

Furthermore, our SHAP analysis revealed a balanced contribution from all three modalities in the final model. This provides a mechanistic explanation for our core finding: by providing the classifier with three independent, high-fidelity feature streams, we allow it to learn the complex, non-linear interactions that are essential for accurate treatment outcome—interactions that may be obscured or lost when information is prematurely integrated into a single narrative.

While our framework demonstrates significant promise, several limitations provide important context for our findings and represent key avenues for future work. First, this study is based on a retrospective cohort from a single institution with a modest sample size (N=184). Indeed, the central motivation of our 'semantic summarization' methodology was to maximize the predictive signal from such data-scarce environments. While our rigorous cross-validation provides confidence in the stability of our results, external validation on larger, multi-center datasets is a critical next step to confirm the generalizability of our model.

Second, our analysis was limited to the structured and semi-structured data available in the EHR. Our LLM's input is not truly "raw" data. This was a deliberate design choice to enhance stability and reduce the risk of hallucination by grounding the LLM's task in curated biomedical databases (e.g., DrugBank, GO, KEGG). However, we did not incorporate other powerful modalities such as unstructured clinical notes or pathology reports, which contain critical information like precise tumor staging. Integrating these text-heavy sources is a significant but distinct research challenge that represents a promising future direction for our framework.

Third, a limitation of this proof-of-concept study is its reliance on proprietary APIs for its core components (e.g., Gemini 2.0 Flash for summarization and Gecko for embedding). To assess the practical feasibility of this approach, we conducted an analysis of its technical efficiency. (1) Computational Cost: Based on the average token usage per patient (approx. 3,144 input tokens for summarization, 1,622 output tokens for summarization, and 1,622 tokens for embedding), the total computational cost is approximately \$0.00099 per patient. This extremely low cost suggests that the direct expense of our framework is highly feasible for both large-scale research and potential clinical application. (2) Latency: We also measured the end-to-end processing time required to generate a full multimodal summary for a single patient, which averaged 1.6 seconds. This rapid response time is practical for many clinical decision support scenarios where near-real-time results are valuable.

Finally, we employed a 90-day landmark design to handle temporal data, a standard and robust approach to mitigate bias. However, we have not systematically explored more complex methods for modeling longitudinal data, which could potentially extract even deeper insights from the patient's trajectory over time.

There are several avenues for future work. Validation on larger, multi-institutional, and prospective cohorts is essential. Expanding to other cancers and incorporating additional modalities (e.g., imaging, pathology reports) could further improve robustness and generalizability. The interpretability and modularity of our framework may also support integration into clinical decision-support tools.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we confronted the challenge of prediction of treatment outcomes from sparse, real-world clinical data. We hypothesized that the limitations of traditional numerical features could be overcome by leveraging LLMs to generate high-quality, semantically rich features. To test this, we developed a novel 'Goal-oriented Knowledge Curator' framework, where LLMs transform raw, multi-modal data (Lab, Genomics, Medication) into modality-specific modality summaries. Our experiments systematically demonstrated the superiority of this approach, with our final model achieving best performance with AUC-ROC of 0.803 and AUC-PRC of 0.859. The primary contribution of this study is the finding that the optimal role for LLMs in this domain is as goal-oriented knowledge curators, generating high-fidelity intermediate features for a downstream classifier. By capturing the complementary interplay among the biological 'blueprint' (Genomics),

physiological 'state' (Lab), and therapeutic 'trajectory' (Medication), our approach delivers a new computational paradigm with immediate clinical relevance and broad future applicability for precision medicine in data-scarce environments.

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